

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium with Isonitrosothiocamphor[†]

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Manuscript received 21 December 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of palladium(II) in microgram level has been developed on the basis of the results obtained in the extraction study. Palladium(II) forms a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex with isonitrosothiocamphor (INTC). Quantitative extraction of the complex into chloroform occurs from 5 M hydrochloric acid to pH 2. Beer's law is obeyed at 450 nm over the palladium concentration range 3-25 ppm. The system tolerates 4 to 50-fold excess of diverse ions. Mercury(II) and thiosulphate interfere. Molar absorptivity of the complex was calculated to be $3.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 450 nm and sensitivity $0.025 \mu\text{g}$ palladium.

LITERATURE survey reveals the use of a number of complexing agents to determine palladium in presence of other diverse ions. Oximes, xanthates, β -diketones and other chelating agents¹ come to the forefront in this connection. Some thiocompounds² have also been used. The use of isonitrosothiocamphor (INTC) is under investigation in our laboratory. In the present communication we report the analytical application of the reagent towards palladium. In slightly acidic medium palladium forms a reddish brown complex extractable into chloroform. Beer's law is valid over a concentration range of 3-25 ppm palladium at 450 nm. The operation is simple and rapid. Effect of pH, reagent concentration, shaking period, diverse ions etc. on the extraction behaviour have been studied. The nature of the extracted species has also been investigated.

Experimental

A Beckman DU 2 spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (10 mm path length) was used for optical density measurements. An Elico pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Chloroform (B.D.H.) was distilled before use. Isonitrosothiocamphor was prepared in the laboratory by the reported method³ and a 0.5% (w/v) solution of the reagent in ethanol was used. Palladium(II) stock solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g PdCl₂ (Johnson Matthey) in 1 ml concentrated HCl and diluted to 250 ml with double-distilled water and standardised with dimethylglyoxime⁴. Standard solution of diverse ions were prepared from their chloride or sulphate, or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. Dilute HCl and NaOH were used to maintain different pH. All

chemicals were either chemically pure or of reagent grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Photometric determination of palladium: An aliquot containing 450 μg palladium(II) was taken in a separating funnel and mixed with adequate amount of HCl to have the desired acidity and to maintain the aqueous phase at 20 ml throughout the work. The reagent solution (1 ml, 0.5%) was then added and kept for 2 min to ensure complete complexation. Foreign ions were added before the addition of HCl to evaluate their interferences. To study the effect of pH, dilute HCl and NaOH were added accordingly. The reddish brown Pd^{II}-chelate formed was extracted with chloroform (20 ml) for 2 min followed by washing of the aqueous phase with 2 \times 2 ml chloroform to avoid loss. The chloroform phase was transferred and diluted to 25 ml with chloroform, and its absorbance was measured at 450 nm against reagent blank and palladium was determined from a previously prepared calibration curve. The chloroform extract may be shaken with anhydrous sodium sulphate prior to the absorption measurement step to remove any retained water. All the experiments were carried out at 26-30°.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum and effect of acidity: The spectrum of Pd^{II}-isonitrosothiocamphor complex in chloroform extracted as above has a broad band showing maximum absorbance at 450 nm. Variation of pH in aqueous medium has no effect on the pattern of the spectrum. The reagent does not reveal absorption in this region in the identical conditions. All the measurements were carried out

[†] Presented in the National Symposium on Absorption Spectrometry held in Bombay in 1984.

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at 450 nm. Quantitative extraction of Pd^{II} occurs from 5 M HCl to pH 2. Above or below this range extraction was found to be incomplete.

Calibration curve : Different amounts of palladium were extracted quantitatively as described earlier at 1 M HCl and the chloroform extract was measured at 450 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. After extraction the aqueous phase was evaporated to dryness followed by spot test which proved the absence of palladium in each case. The results indicate that the system obeys Beer's law at 450 nm over a concentration range of 3-25 ppm of palladium.

Reagent concentration and shaking period : Keeping the other variables constant, variation of reagent concentration was tested in 1 M HCl medium. 1 ml of 0.5% (w/v) ethanolic solution of the reagent was found to be sufficient to extract 450 µg palladium. Use of 0.4 ml of 0.5% reagent solution renders the procedure time consuming. Higher concentration (> 1 ml, 0.5%) had no adverse effect but was avoided due to reagent economy. Palladium (450 µg) is extracted quantitatively into chloroform in a single operation when the layers are shaken for 2 min. A 2 min-period was as sufficient as 5 or 10 min-period.

Some aspects of the nature of Pd^{II}-INTC chelate : The nature of the extracted species was ascertained from the mole-ratio method. The results indicate that the metal to reagent ratio in the complex is 1 : 2. The optical density of the chloroform extract containing 450 µg palladium extracted as above was measured at different intervals of time showing that colour of the complex is stable at least for 36 h. At the end of 48 h, the absorbance decreases by about 3%. It is thereby convenient to measure the optical densities within 36 h after the extraction. The molar absorptivity of the complex was calculated to be $3.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (on the basis of palladium content) and sensitivity in terms of Sandell's definition being 0.025 µg Pd.

Interference : The effect of diverse ions on the palladium(II) determination was studied by carrying out the extraction at 1 M HCl, unless otherwise mentioned, in presence of a definite amount of a foreign ion. In the estimation of 450 µg Pd, the following ions did not cause deviation of more than $\pm 3\%$ in absorbance when present in amounts (mg) shown in parentheses: Ca^{II} (25), Ba^{II} (25), Sr^{II} (25), Cd^{II} (10), Pb^{II} (20), Zr^{IV} (25), Th^{IV} (20), U^{VI} (25), Ni^{II} (10), Rh^{III} (5), Zn^{II} (25), Cr^{III} (25), Fe^{II} (25), Fe^{III} (25), Mn^{II} (20), Mg^{II} (25), Al^{III} (25), citrate (40), acetate (50), molybdate (25), fluoride (20), EDTA (10), sulphate (50), oxalate (50), phosphate (50), borate (50), tartrate (50), nitrate (50). Pt^{IV} (4) and Co^{II} (4) were tolerated in the system provided the extraction be carried out at pH 2 and 4 M HCl respectively. Cu^{II} (25) did not interfere in presence of tartrate. High results were obtained in presence of Hg^{II} and all attempts to mask it failed. Thiosulphate inhibited the colour formation in the aqueous phase.

The results are accurate within $\pm 2.5\%$, rendering the proposed method fairly precise and reproducible. The process is rapid and simple. The total operation for each run requires only 15-20 min.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, for facilities.

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